

Postindustrial Frameworks: beginning design studies in the third age of production

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Introduction

Since the mid-twentieth century, postindustrial transformation into the information age has induced a series of consequential but piecemeal changes in design education. Aside from educational tools and strategies; this transformation impacts design methods, techniques of fabrication and, most importantly, the societal institutions that designers serve. Our sequential but intermittent responses to the advent of computational decision-making, cybernetic feedback, integrated systems, evidence-based validation, sustainability, human capital, and other emergent aspects of information society continue to encourage such educational innovation. In light of the fractured and episodic nature of our response to change however, we must now ask how the basic premise of design should be proactively reframed as a radical new idea for a radically new epoch. For

Beginning Design Studies (BDS), this new premise should be made explicit and kept central to our students' education.

The History

The historical emergence of postindustrial society, and its impact on design across the ages are condensed here as tables. Table 1 introduces postindustrial society as the third age of production and shows agreement between the primary historical and social research. The bases of historical transition are determined by the primary means of value production as employment shifted in developed countries steadily away from agriculture and industry and moved instead toward service workers in the knowledge economy. Significantly, postindustrial change is viewed quite positively as a correction of industrial era tenden-

Table 1. Social ideals and the three ages of production as a story about civilization.¹

	Geddes 1915	Mumford 1934	Fourastié 1979	Bell 1973
1.	EOTECHNIC Life in Balance -Raw material production	EOTECHNIC 1000 to 1700 -Village life, coal and steel -Intensification of life	PRIMARY Traditional -70% agriculture -20% industry -10% service	PREINDUSTRIAL -Agriculture and mining -Raw material basis of production
2.	PALEOTECHNIC: Life Threatened -Private dispensation of resources -Resources for individual gain	PALEOTECHNIC- 1700 to 1900 -Industrial Megapolis -Profit overrides general principles	SECONDARY -Trente Glorieuses 20-50-30 % employment sectors	INDUSTRIAL -Practical know-how -Productive labor
3.	EUTECHNIC- Life Resurgent -Public conservation of resources -Evolution of public good, social equity	NEOTECHNIC- 1934 forward -Organic human scale living -Science, communication, information	TERTIARY -Education, culture, social equity 10-20-70 % employment	POSTINDUSTRIAL -Human capital, automation -Intellectual technology, network society

Table 2: Three eras of design in the three eras of production.^v

	PRE INDUSTRIAL Before about 1700 The Eotechnic	INDUSTRIAL 1700 to the present The Paleotechnic	POST INDUSTRIAL The evolving present The Neotechnic
Design	Craft and design synonymous	Design as a profession	Design as a discipline
Materials	Raw materials	Mass standardization	Mass customization
Knowledge	Static	Incremental shifts	Continuous change
Cosmology	Mythical explanations	Anthropocentric	Biocentric
Order	Holistic	Hierarchical	Holistic
Development	Refine the prototype	Test unique artifact	Simulate possible artifacts
Change	Conformity	Novelty	Evolutionary
Instrument	Nature as the model	Drawings	Virtual simulations
Method	Normative rules	Policies and procedures	Cybernetic knowledge
Perspective	Holistic	Components in isolation	Integrated systems
Dynamics	Innocent naivety	Self-referential	Embodied intelligence
Lifecycle	Degrade	Use and dispose	Reprocess as nutrient
Solutions	Transient	Fragile & fragmentary	Robust
Effort	Communal	Individual	Team
Educate	Trade apprentice	University: liberal study	Explicit and synthetic
Collaboration	Mono-disciplinary guilds	Multidisciplinary	Transdisciplinary
Application	Need	Art for the elite	Sustain societal goals

cies; most notably those negative aspects towards personal gratification and instant profit. The postindustrial promise is rather that of long term investment and social equity. A century ago, Patrick Geddes and Louis Mumford had already co-developed visions of the third age of production that closely correspond to our contemporary circumstances.ⁱⁱ The opportunity to reformulate the corollary premise of design is now at hand.

Table 2 compares some defining features of the three ages of production with special reference to the corresponding attributes of design in each epoch. Here too the design prospects of postindustrial change are positive, as befits the

Table 3 Postindustrial professionsⁱⁱⁱ

Physics	Quantum mechanics and the Unified Field Theory (Bohr, Heisenberg, Hawking)
Engineering	Non-linear and chaotic systems
Psychology	Self-actualization and psychosynthesis (Maslow, Graf)
Sociology	Knowledge based culture (Kuhn)
Business	Industrial Organization Psychology
Medicine	Holistic health and mind/body healing (Chopra)
Agriculture	Organic gardening and beneficial insects (Rodale)
Economics	Life-cycle costs and externalized accounting (Henderson)

progress of civilization. Although industrial age advances doubled human life expectancy against infectious diseases of nature, brought about mechanized transport, gave us digital communication, and automated many slavish aspects of human labor; it also commoditized nature as both a resource and waste site, encouraged consumer based capitalism, and led to a whole new morbidity of industrial disease cancer, toxic materials, spoiled nature, and sick buildings.^{iv}

Ultimately, in this new information driven society, the last and only profession is that of design—or put another way, all professions must have design as a primary concern: Architects design buildings; teachers design curricula, doctors design cures, judges design law, scientists design experiments, and so forth. Inherent in this third age of ubiquitous design is the recognition that design is broadly about how we invent a better future (Table 3). That acknowledgement valorizes design as a champion of progress, and also saddles it with the responsibility to think long-term and recognize interdependencies.

The Problem

For BDS, our piecemeal response to the symptoms of this emerging third era of production misses the essential systemic underlying root cause. We have

thus been left to a positive but fragmented, inch-by-inch series of changes in our corresponding educational efforts. It is time now for a holistic reconfiguration of the BDS mission. As Thomas Kuhn portrays paradigm shifts, the existing circumstances of BDS are ripe for new theory to reunite its educational practices.^{vi}

Central to this argument is the notion that BDS must accurately and honestly portray the mission of design. Beginning design students must then be presented with this mission challenge in explicit terms, and held accountable for the relevance of design in a changing time.

In place of the industrial era role of design then, we must offer the beginning design student a rationale that embraces:

1. theory over expertise and talent—for only theory enables us to make sense of new, unique, and complex problems;
2. transdisciplinary teamwork over Balkanized multidisciplinary approaches and heroic individualism—because embodying human intelligence in design requires many kinds of thinking;
3. evidence based validation over expressionism—because underlying issues are core;
4. parametric driven processes in tandem with opportunistic exploration—as design is both rational and intuitive;
5. clinical insight over privileged intuition—as feedback from use in place corrects our understanding;
6. social based validation in tandem with cultural values—because society is always the ultimate client;
7. shared authorship and mutual validation over assumptions of talent and genius—because design is a learnable skill, while designing is a collaborative and participatory activity, and;

8. a new synthesis of form and function—as whole-minded design cannot compromise between sublime human significance and strategic human foresight.

Moving beyond the industrial era mindset requires more strategic and long-term thinking. Piecemeal, stepwise, and near-term planning for immediate gratification and quick profit are all stigma of the “short-termism” we must transcend. Recent commentary by Bordass and Lehman on built environment professions summarizes that:

“Most authors agree that professionalism has been eroded by short-termism, bureaucracy and outsourcing of technical skills by government. Accountability is replacing trust, reflecting what has been happening in wider society—the unintended consequence of replacing ethics by rules and regulations, and leaving everything else to the invisible hand of the free market. [. . .] Urgent challenges include dealing with rapid growth in developing countries, diminished resources in developed ones, and sustainability everywhere.”^{vii}

Another such issue of postindustrial transition for the design professions is that of corporate management. For example, as more and more architects work for larger firms, those individuals make the conscious bargain of surrendering independence and personal authorship in turn for security and teamwork. One result of this arrangement is what Garry Stevens identifies as the prevalence of a very few “major” architects and the proliferation of many “minor” architects^{viii}. Statistically, about 30% of all U.S. architects work for the 175 firms employing more than 100 architects. Another 20% or so work in firms of 50 to 99 total employees. The same data state that the 1% of firms over 100 employees accounts for more than 33% of all billings while sole practitioners account for about 2%.^{ix}

This point on corporate management is not to stratify classes of architects or infer that a large

firm architect is less likely to succeed in their career, but rather to point out that this trend is contrary to the image many beginning architecture students have of the ideal career where they aspire to personal recognition and name brand authorship of significant buildings. In parallel with the “short-termism” erosion of public trust in the value and altruistic commitment of design professionals from outside the design community; there is also an ongoing distillation of design authorship happening from within. The beginning design student should be made aware of these trends as part of their initial premise for taking up a design career.

Complexity and Dynamic Systems

What then are the promises of postindustrial transition? The answers lie in the interconnected nature of information society, knowledge work, and evidence based accountability. In contrast to the linear dead-end short-termism of industrial era mechanistic thinking, our emerging third age of production embraces life-cycle holistic perspectives of interactive, and interdependent complexity. In turn, the key to this complexity is found in dynamic systems. The attributes of that complexity are evident in all traces of postindustrial transformation: sustainability, globalization, transdisciplinary teamwork, and life-cycle investment to list just a few examples of radical departure from the old corresponding attributes of consumption, isolation, heroic individualism, and short-term profit. In all cases, the shift from short-termism and mechanistic oversimplification give way to farsighted wisdom.

For the beginning design student, this transition to complexity is not a complication that is eventually acquired as advanced knowledge later in the curriculum. It is in fact a fundamental precept that must inform and inspire design education from the first day of initiation into one’s personal identity as a designer. It would be a great disservice to ground a student’s first precepts of design in the old industrial paradigm.

So from the model of mechanistic isolation and hierarchical order, we move to the model of complex dynamic systems and deep interrelatedness. Animate organisms in nature are the best examples of such dynamic systems. Characteristically, these complex organisms exhibit a feedback loop with their environment based on energy, matter or information flows where organisms adapt to fulfill their purpose. This feedback is the basis of what we call cybernetics (from the Greek “to steer”). Dynamic systems are not only adaptive however, they are also self-organizing and self-regulating.

Another touchstone to BDS complexity is offered by the postpositive philosopher of science, Karl Popper and his Three Worlds ontology (Table. 4 and Figure. 1).^x For Popper, world 3 is filled with high level constructs of the human mind, fashioned by discourse and hardened by critique. Moreover, these world 3 constructs come about through intersubjective agreement and so are different from world two personal truths. Getting the beginning design student from world 2 personal subjectivity to world 3 shared discourse is part of the requisite complexity.

A comparison of Table 2 and Table 4 illustrates sympathy between postindustrial and postpositive programs with special distinction between mechanistic industrial versus systems-based postindustrial thought. For Popper, the difference parallels that of the transit from world 2 truths to world 3 truths.

Aesthetics: Cognitive Affect and Effect

“Aesthetics conveys the interdependence of our appreciation [affect] and our understanding [effect].” (Roger Scruton, 1979)

“The ontological function of the beautiful is to bridge the chasm between the real [effect] and the ideal [affect].” (Hans Georg Gadamer, 1960)

“A universe that displays local phenomena [affect] built on nonlocal reality [effect] is

Table 4. The author’s interpretation of Karl Popper’s Three Worlds ontology¹

World One	World Two	World Three
Objective Fact	Personal cognition	Shared constructions
Science	Experience	Philosophy
Strategic sphere	Physical sphere	Holistic approaches
Objects, States, and Systems	Perceptions	Culture
Physics, Chemistry, Biology	Personal Intuition	Virtual Knowledge
Things as they are	Subjective Impressions	Intersubjective agreement
Facts	Understanding	Discourse and critique
Data	Information	Wisdom
Knowledge	Expertise	Theory
Dualistic	Multiplicity	Pluralistic
Observation	Analysis	Synthesis
Declarative	Procedural	Structural
Truth	Conduct	Authenticity
Noumena	Phenomena	Ethos
Non-local order	Local-order	Aesthetics
Spontaneous	Intentional	Relational
Discovery	Invention	Coherence
Entropy	Order	Sustainable

the only sort of world consistent with known facts...” (Bohm 1980)

[“Affect” and “Effect” insertions are by the author.]^{xi}

Taking the full definition of aesthetics as the study of human appreciation rather than its oversimplification as the value of beauty, a cognitive model emerges for the adaptation of complex dynamic systems into BDS. In this model, left brain rational

effect and right brain emotive affect are connected, interdependent, and bridged by the act of design. The connection itself is the aesthetic position from which humans appreciate the connectivity of the ideal affect and the real effect. This connection is also the distinction between the brain organ and the conscious mind.^{xii} Design is the ideal made whole and concrete. Mind is similarly animation by complexity. Some more explicit parallels of left and right brain thinking are given in Table 5.^{xiii}

A new aesthetic embracing the third age of production, design, and civilization will ultimately evolve as authentic response to the radical transformations that are inherent in what Mies van der Rohe called “the will of the epoch.” One source of such an aesthetic is that of philosophical hermeneutics. A propositional sketch of that connective basis is offered here (Fig. 2). Aside from the

Figure 1. The author’s graphic interpretation of Popper’s Three Worlds ontology.

Table 5. The Two Sphere Tandems

Right Brain Physical Aspect	Left Brain Strategic Aspect
Affect	Effect
Immediacy	Foresight
Significance	Intelligence
Emotive	Rational
Immeasurable	Measureable
The Ideal	The Real

Figure 2. Aesthetics as a bridge between complimentary pairs: real and ideal, strategic and physical, measurable and immeasurable.

sources already cited, readers may recognize Louis Kahn's "measurable and immeasurable" in the diagram.^{xiv}

Negative examples are well-suited to illustrate the complex whole of this aesthetic connection. First, consider Mary Shelly's *Frankenstein*: a foreboding tale of the dangers of industrial mechanization; depicted in the creature Adam as an invention whose parts were mechanically correct, but whose being was never animated by the true complexity of a holistic entity. Adam was always a machine, no matter the care given to its conception, parts, or anatomical assembly. Similarly, contrast the mechanism of a tree farm with the ecology of a forest. To make less and less wood of ever declining quality, the tree farm requires increasing levels of fertilizer, pesticide, and herbicide; precisely because it is working against nature to maintain an artificial monoculture of linear throughput processes. The forest on the other hand is a robust and self-organizing dynamic system of cyclical flows where events feed into one another. And should the tree farm be burned down by lightning, it is lost forever. The forest however would reemerge from the ashes.

Conclusion

Dear Beginning Design Student:

We know that you already hold design in your heart as a way to make a better world; and we know that you believe you will one day personally do great things to that end. We are here to help you become that person. Before we get started however, it is necessary that we frame the mission, goals, and tactics of your design education in an authentic and honest way. To achieve that framing, it is necessary to set yourself accurately into the social context within which design now operates.

We are moving into a third age of production, thought, and civilization; an age in which the deterministic and machine-centered industrial era is giving way to a cybernetic and organic approach to design and moving us into a society of postindustrial values. In this new era, your work will not be judged on its sublime physical expression alone, nor just on its high-performing strategic intelligence, but rather on how well you can bridge between the two; for that is the ultimate role of

design, and we have arrived at the realization: We can make this happen.

You will live and work in a dynamic set of interactive relations that will periodically redefine your career. You will deal with increasingly complex problems for which there are no precedent designs and no robust solutions. Your assumptions will be scientifically tested and your decisions will be user validated. The ongoing use of your designs will change over time. Adaptability and flexibility will have to be incorporated in the initial state.

The tools you use and the methods of their application will be increasingly sophisticated and information based. The systems and components you incorporate into your designs will likewise be highly integrated in their functions and interactive in their use. These systems will listen to you, talk to each other, and they will speak back to us in their own voices.

Your autonomy as a professional will be under pressure and your judgment will always be questioned. Public trust in your altruistic service and

your benevolent intentions will have to be earned and re-earned. You will always work in a team environment; even as a sole practitioner: with project members ranging from owners, users, suppliers, fabricators, technical consultants, and government agencies. They will all push you. Some of these people will be far away and come from other cultures, but they will never leave you alone. Expect to share authorship of design with them all.

We will build more new things and invoke more new ideas in the next thirty years than we have in the last 30,000. The resources needed to make that happen will be precious, and the waste by-products of production, operation, repair, and disposal will be restricted; so we can't afford for you to get this huge project wrong. The world depends on the legacy of what you produce. Please be wise and prudent. Make something we love, but don't pretend there is someplace called "Away" where resources come from and waste goes to. You own the providence of it all.

Notes

ⁱ Leonard Bachman. 2013. *Embracing Complexity in Architectural Learning*. ASCE Centennial Conference, Corpus Christi, Texas.

ⁱⁱ Patrick Geddes and Lewis Mumford jointly coined the Eo-, Paleo-, and Neo-Technic terms to frame history into three eras of production. Daniel Bell later documented the actual 1950s onset of postindustrial society.

ⁱⁱⁱ Leonard Bachman. 2012. *Cybertown: the other façade of the postindustrial city*. ARCC/EAAE International Conference on Architectural Research, Milan, Italy, June 2012.

^{iv} Leonard Bachman. 2012. *Two Spheres: Physical and Strategic Design in Architecture*. London ; New York: Routledge.

^{iv} In 1900, the leading causes of death in the United States were influenza, pneumonia, and tooth infection; and the average life expectancy of a new-borne child was 48. In 2000 a new borne's life expectancy was 77 and the leading causes of death were heart disease and cancer. See the Center for Disease Control; accessed 12 December 2014:

http://www.cdc.gov/nchs/data/dvs/lead1900_98.pdf

^{vi} Thomas Kuhn. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1st ed.). University of Chicago Press.

^{vii} Bill Bordass and Adrian Lehman. 2013. *Editorial: A New Professionalism: remedy or fantasy?* Building Research and Information, Vol. 41. No.1 (See this complete special *New Professionalism* theme issue) and Leonard Bachman. 2013. *New Professionalism: the post-industrial context*, Building Re-

search & Information Vol. 41, No. 6, 2013. Accessed 18 December 2014
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09613218.2013.804778>

viii Garry Stevens. 2002. *The Favored Circle: The Social Foundations of Architectural Distinction*. Cambridge, Mass.; London: The MIT Press. 142

ix AIA. 2014. AIA Architect, *Practicing Architecture: get on the good foot*. Accessed 1 December 2014. <http://www.aia.org/practicing/AIAB104583>; I. Vinnitskaya. 2013. *AIA/NCARB Survey Indicates Resurgence in Employment Rates for Architects* 15 Apr 2013. ArchDaily. Accessed 05 Dec 2014. <http://www.archdaily.com/?p=359798>

x Karl Popper. 1978. *The Tanner Lectures on Human Values: Three Worlds*. University of London.

Accessed 30 November 2014. <http://tanner-lectures.utah.edu/documents/a-to-z/p/popper80.pdf>.

xi Roger Scruton. 1979. *The Aesthetics of Architecture*. Methuen; Gadamer, Hans Georg, Joel Weinsheimer, and Donald G. Marshall. 2004. *Truth and Method*. Continuum International Publishing Group; Bohm, David. 1980. *Wholeness and the Implicate Order*. London; Boston: Routledge & Kegan Paul.

xii Scott Kelso. 1999. *Dynamic Patterns: The Self-Organization of Brain and Behavior*. Cambridge, MA; London: The MIT Press.

xiii Ibid.

xiv Quoted in R. Twombly (ed.) 2003. *Louis Kahn: Essential Texts*, New York: W. W. Norton.